

High-resolution 3D CFD simulations of wind turbine aerofoils with 3D scanned leading edge roughness

Alexander Meyer Forsting* Antariksh Dicholkar† Niels N Sørensen‡ and Anders S Olsen§
DTU Wind & Energy Systems, Roskilde, DK 4000, Denmark

The impact of leading edge roughness (LER) and erosion on wind turbine aerodynamic performance remains highly uncertain, due to a lack of high-resolution topographic roughness data of in-service blades. Within the LERCat project headed by DTU Wind a workflow was established that extracts roughness topographies from high-resolution 3D scans of real-world LER and applies them digitally to any other aerofoil surface that can be assessed aerodynamically using 3D CFD or wind tunnels. Two of the extracted roughness topographies—one with few spanwise distributed shallow damages (≤ 0.8 mm) towards the suction side and another with deep erosion (≤ 4.0 mm) all along the span—are applied to two commonly used wind turbine aerofoils with 21% and 25% relative thickness and evaluated with RANS CFD by highly resolving (≈ 100 μm) the erosion damages. The effect of roughness on boundary layer transition is evaluated by using the γ - $\text{Re}_{\theta t}$ transition model; simulations are performed at Reynolds numbers of 3 and 6 million. The aerofoils react similarly to the tested erosion, with the shallow damages triggering transition on the suction side over the entire span around operating angles-of-attack at 6 million. Pressure side transition is not affected as the stagnation point moves below the eroded region. The deep erosion on the other not only triggers transition, increasing viscous drag, but also strongly increases pressure drag when approaching stall. Furthermore 2D chordwise slices are extracted from the 3D aerofoil with LER and simulated to quantify the error from using 2D representations of 3D LER for evaluating roughness related aerodynamic performance loss.

I. Introduction

WIND turbine blades operate under harsh environmental conditions throughout their lifespan—easily exceeding 20 years—especially exposing the blade leading edge (LE) to damage (e.g., from rain, hail, sand, sea spray) and contamination (e.g., insects, pollen, ice) with severe implications regarding aerodynamic performance [1–4]. Together with icing, LE erosion and roughness (LER) creates the aerodynamically most detrimental topographic surface imperfections. Hence within the industry LER related aerodynamic performance losses are expected, but their magnitude can only be roughly estimated, due to a lack of high-resolution LER data from full-scale, in-service blades [1, 5–7]. Modern wind turbine aerofoils are operating at Reynolds numbers between 5 to 20 million which requires a spatial surface resolution of at least 50-100 μm to capture aerodynamically relevant surface features [5, 8], which can only be provided by high-resolution 3D optical, laser or computed tomography (CT) scanners, making it difficult to obtain such data from full-scale blades.

Within the Leading Edge Roughness Categorisation (LERCat) project*, headed by DTU Wind, castings and laser scans of in-service or decommissioned blades exhibiting LER of varying severity were performed. A workflow was established that extracts roughness topographies from those high-resolution 3D scans and applies them digitally to any other aerofoil surface that can subsequently be assessed aerodynamically using 3D CFD or wind tunnels [9]. As shown by Stebbins *et al.* [10, 11] for LE icing, RANS accurately captures even complex flow features around and within complex LE surface topographies, especially at lower angles-of-attack, as also demonstrated by Bons *et al.* [12] for a patch of resolved gas turbine blade roughness. Due to the computational cost of resolving LER—in the order of 100 μm surface resolution is required at relevant Reynolds numbers—existing CFD investigations of wind turbine LER rely on simulating 2D slices [6, 7, 13] or reducing the complexity of the erosion [14].

*Senior Researcher, DTU Wind & Energy Systems, alrf@dtu.dk.

†Researcher, DTU Wind & Energy Systems, acdi@dtu.dk.

‡Professor, DTU Wind & Energy Systems, nsqr@dtu.dk.

§Senior Development Engineer, DTU Wind & Energy Systems, sols@dtu.dk

*Sponsored by the Danish Energy Council; Partners: DTU Wind, Vestas Wind Systems A/S, Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy A/S, LM Wind Power A/S, Suzlon Energy Netherlands Branch, PowerCurve ApS

Hence in this paper two roughness topographies recently extracted from high-resolution 3D scans (10 – 100 μm point-to-point distance) of LER on wind turbine blades are applied to two commonly used wind turbine aerofoils with 21% and 25% relative thickness shown in figure 1—the FFA21-W3-211 [15] and DU91-W2-250 [16] aerofoils—and evaluated in RANS CFD, thereby also establishing how different aerofoil designs respond to LER. The two topographies are very distinct, with one exhibiting a sparse distribution of damages of limited depth (≤ 0.8 mm) towards the suction side and the other deep, spanwise-uniform erosion (≤ 4 mm) with sharp forward facing steps and overhangs. The focus lies in attributing departures from clean aerofoil performance in terms of integral measures to LER induced alterations at the boundary layer level over a wide angle-of-attack range. Whether the LER triggers premature transition is evaluated by running the simulations with the $\gamma\text{-}Re_{\theta t}$ transition model. Furthermore 2D chordwise slices are extracted from the 3D aerofoil with LER and simulated to quantify the error from using 2D representations of 3D LER for evaluating roughness related aerodynamic performance loss.

Fig. 1 The two wind turbine aerofoils investigated with 21% and 25% relative thickness.

II. Digital Leading Edge Roughness

A. Workflow Overview

Figure 2 presents the workflow developed at DTU Wind underlying the generation of 3D aerofoil surfaces with LER from measured 3D point-clouds and their aerodynamic evaluation. An important feature of the workflow is the equivalence between the aerofoil surface simulated and tested, which allows cross-validating the numerical and experimental methods used. A detailed description of each process involved in building the digital LER can be found in [9], but it essentially constitutes the acquisition—direct hand-held 3D laser scans of blade leading edges or lab scans of gypsum castings from imprints—the removal of the underlying aerofoil shape or extraction of the roughness map, its post-processing and mapping it onto another, clean profile. The LE of the 3D surface is then either 3D printed and attached to a wind tunnel model or acts as the starting mesh layer in the volume mesh generation. The entire meshing process is automatized in a single Python-based workflow named AeroMesher, that heavily relies on the functionalities provided by the open-source Parametric Geometry Library for Wind (PGLW) [17] and in-house Fortran meshing tools accessible through the PyEllipSys Python interface. AeroMesher process blocks are outlined by a dashed line in figure 2.

B. Selected Roughness Maps

Figure 3 shows top views of the two roughness maps to be evaluated that were selected from several metres of LER surface scans. They are representative of mild (LER1) and severe (LER2) erosion cases found on wind turbine blades. The roughness maps are in blade surface following coordinates, with the chordwise coordinate s , origin at the LE and positive towards the suction side, the spanwise coordinate, t , positive towards the blade tip and the surface normal coordinate, n , pointing outwards and nil in absence of roughness. The spanwise extent of both maps is 95 mm, whilst the chordwise extents are 24 and 44 mm, respectively. As the roughness maps were uniformly resolved, the bounds were chosen to minimise the computational mesh size. Note that both maps are not centred about the LE, but cover varying fractions of the pressure and suction side. As outlined in [9] 10 mm of the original cloud point roughness data are lost in the spanwise direction to enforce spanwise periodicity. The roughness patches were mapped onto the aerofoil coordinate system without any re-scaling.

Fig. 2 Digital LER creation and aerodynamic assessment workflow implemented within the LERCat project. The wind tunnel procedure is not detailed herein.

Fig. 3 Mild (LER1) and severe (LER2) wind turbine blade erosion roughness maps in blade surface following coordinate system with n pointing outwards.

C. Computational Mesh

Figure 4 shows an illustration of the structured, 3D O-type volume mesh employed. It consists of two components, an inner hyperbolic/transfinite topology and an outer fractal style domain. This composition allows generating a high-resolution volume mesh of elevated quality over the LER topography—orthogonal and topography following—without having excessive resolution and high-aspect ratio cells in the farfield. Its generation is orchestrated through AeroMesher using the PyEllipSys Python interfaces to the in-house hyperbolic structured grid generators HypGrid2D/3D [18] and the mesh pre-processor Basis3D [19] together with the mesh manipulation tools from PGLW [17]. The radius of the O-mesh is $45c$, with c denoting the aerofoil chord length (900 mm), whereas the spanwise extent is $0.1c$. The span- and chordwise grid spacing over the LER surface is $110 \mu\text{m}$ and $106 \mu\text{m}$, respectively, and uniform. The respective LER surfaces are rendered in figure 5. The resolution remains unchanged between mild and severe erosion, thus resulting in 864 spanwise and 768,960 chordwise cells. The first normal cell size is $1 \times 10^{-6}c$. The normal mesh spacing grows from the surface at a rate of 1.08 until reaching the end of the hyperbolic mesh region $0.05c$ from the surface, using 128 cells. The same number of cells is used until reaching the first spanwise fractal reduction layer at $1.10c$ (reduction by 9) followed by another at $1.15c$ (reduction by 3). In total 353 normal cells are used. The fractal topology significantly reduces the spanwise grid resolution away from the aerofoil, thereby lowering the stiffness of the numerical problem. Note that the fractal reduction layer was initially placed closer to the aerofoil surface (as shown in figure 4). However testing without LER indicated that the high skewness introduced by the fractals lead to artificial production of vorticity and eddy viscosity, which was transported into the boundary layer, causing premature transition. Placing the first fractal reduction layer $1.10c$ away from the aerofoil surface avoids this, as gradients are significantly smaller there. The in- and outflow boundary conditions are applied dynamically depending on the angle-of-attack and the spanwise boundaries are periodic.

Fig. 4 Colour-coded components of the 3D O-type structured volume mesh with uniformly high resolution around the leading edge of the FFA-W3-211 aerofoil (reproduced from [9]).

Fig. 5 Rendering of the surface mesh for the mild (LER1) and severe (LER2) erosion roughness maps wrapped over the FFA-W3-211 aerofoil.

D. Solver and Simulation Setup

The simulations are performed with DTU Wind’s in-house incompressible finite-volume flow solver, EllipSys [19, 20], which employs structured grids and a cell-centred finite volume formulation with a multiblock approach for parallelisation. The pressure-correction problem is solved using an efficient multigrid algorithm and convergence is accelerated through grid sequencing. The coupled momentum and pressure-correction equations are solved by using an improved version of the SIMPLEC algorithm [21], and the convective terms are discretized with the third-order accurate QUICK scheme [22]. The RANS equations are closed with Menter’s 2003 version [23] of the $k - \omega$ SST turbulence model. To capture transitional boundary layers the latter is either coupled to the e^N transition model [24–26] implementation by Michelsen [27] or the correlation-based $\gamma-Re_{\theta t}$ model [28]. As demonstrated by Langel et al. [3], the sensitivity of the $\gamma-Re_{\theta t}$ model to the local turbulent kinetic energy requires limiting the excessive and unphysical production of k in the aerofoil stagnation region—caused by high strain rates and inherent to two-equation turbulence models—especially when simulating Reynolds numbers beyond 3 million. This is mitigated by applying the Kato-Launders production limiter [29] instead of the one proposed by Menter as part of the SST model [23]. Similarly, the decay of the freestream turbulent quantities from the inlet boundary towards the aerofoil needs to be avoided, which

is achieved through introducing sustaining terms in the turbulent equations [30]. However these need to be deactivated within the boundary layer to avoid them triggering transition. This is achieved by using the indicator functions (F_1, F_2) of the SST/ γ - $Re_{\theta t}$ model [23]

$$\bullet_{\text{sust}}^* = \bullet_{\text{sust}} \gamma_{\text{eff}} (1 - \max(F_1, F_2)) \quad (1)$$

where \bullet denotes the original sustaining terms proposed for the k and ω equations and γ_{eff} the intermittency that activates turbulent production [28]. As the EllipSys e^N implementation is insensitive to local turbulence levels, the production limiter and sustaining terms have little influence on the results but are still applied for consistency. The N factor is determined from the specified freestream inflow turbulence intensity, Tu_{∞} , following [31].

The inflow conditions for the turbulent conditions are set according to [30], with k_{∞} derived from the freestream turbulence intensity, i.e. $k_{\infty} = 1.5(Tu_{\infty}U_{\infty})^2$, and $\omega_{\infty} = 5U_{\infty}c$, where U_{∞} denotes the freestream velocity magnitude. The Reynolds number is set by changing the viscosity.

III. Results

Fig. 6 Lift-drag polars for the FFA-W3-211 at Reynolds numbers of 3 (upper row) and 6 million (lower row).

A. Clean and Tripped

To verify the CFD setup, first simulations of the clean aerofoils without any erosion are compared to wind tunnel measurements. The 2D predictions are performed with EllipSys2D—the 2D version of the in-house code—and measurements were taken at DTU Wind’s Poul la Cour Tunnel (PLCT). Here the boundary layer was tripped with 0.4 mm tall zig-zag tape positioned at $x/c = 0.05$ on the suction side and $x/c = 0.10$ on the pressure side. Figures 6 and 7 show polars for the FFA and DU aerofoils at two Reynolds numbers, highlighting the impact of Reynolds number and thinning of the boundary layer. The predictions are shown using the e^N and γ - $Re_{\theta t}$ transition models and for the fully turbulent (tripped) case. The performance of the two aerofoils is largely similar with the maximum lift-to-drag ratios lying between 140-150 and occurring at lift coefficients between 1.0-1.25 and angles-of-attack between 5° - 8° . As expected the performance improves with Reynolds number, as the boundary layer becomes thinner, and drops

Fig. 7 Lift-drag polars for the DU91-W2-250 at Reynolds numbers of 3 (*upper row*) and 6 million (*lower row*).

considerably when tripped, affecting the thicker DU aerofoil more strongly, with the maximum glide ratio lying between 60-70 versus 70-80 for the FFA. Whilst the FFA reaches greater maximum lift at slightly larger angles-of-attack (about 2° difference), the measurements also indicate that it stalls very abruptly and loses more lift than the DU. The latter presents quite different behaviour at negative angles-of-attack, with a sudden jump in drag when angles-of-attack fall below 0° . The maximum lift increases with Reynolds number and drops by about 0.15 – 0.20 when tripped.

At angles-of-attack below 7° the predictions and measurements largely coincide, with a slight drag offset for the tripped case at 6 million, potentially stemming from the zig-zag tape being too tall. At greater angles-of-attack the aerofoils begin to stall, which is generally not well captured by 2D simulations, as also seen here. Unfortunately stall is not well captured for thick aerofoils by wind tunnels either, due to corner and blockage effects. The e^N model usually outperforms the $\gamma-Re_{\theta t}$ model in predicting transition, as the latter does not capture the movement of the suction side transition location towards the leading edge correctly as the angle-of-attack grows. In the polars this is reflected by not capturing the drag bucket as well as with the e^N model, thus overestimating the glide ratio at higher lift coefficients. Here this effect diminishes with Reynolds number, though. In the 3D LER simulations only the $\gamma-Re_{\theta t}$ model could be used; the e^N model became numerically unstable, due to the high surface complexity of the roughness topographies. Yet as roughness disturbances are likely to induce premature transition and not the usual free transition mechanism within the model, this is not expected to greatly influence this study. For the FFA furthermore 3D simulations were performed for the clean aerofoil to verify the correct behaviour of the transition model in the high-resolution fractal mesh. The mesh was generated by setting the roughness of LER1 to zero, but otherwise following the erosion meshing procedure outlined in section II.C. Figure 6 indeed proves that the 3D setup performs as the 2D, with only a small offset at 6° around maximum glide ratio at 6 million as transition moves slightly forward by $0.04c$ on the suction side. All clean 3D simulations showed some spanwise variation in the transition location—within $0.02c$ from the mean—likely due to the large spanwise surface resolution and slight asymmetry from the fractal grid topography.

B. Leading Edge Erosion

1. Polars

Figures 6 and 7 also include the span-averaged coefficients for the 3D simulations with mild (LER1) and severe (LER2) erosion. The angle-of-attack resolution is raised around the maximum glide ratio, as this is the usual operational region of these aerofoils. Some simulations at an angle-of-attack of 10° did not converge to a steady-state solution and were hence omitted. At 0° angle-of-attack the lift remains unchanged from the clean transitional, only beyond that does the lift diverge, approaching the tripped clean predictions close to stall. This is more pronounced for the thicker DU aerofoil and at larger Reynolds numbers. As the spanwise extent is limited ($0.1c$) and the simulations are steady-state RANS, the impact of erosion on stall cannot be determined, however the unsteadiness seen at 10° especially for severe erosion indicates that the flow detaches prematurely, similar to the consequences of severe icing [10, 11, 32]. Following the LES icing studies by Bornhoft *et al.* [32], the span extent would have to be at least $0.8c$ to avoid quasi-2D stall behaviour. The drag shows the divergence from clean transitional more clearly, also showing an offset at 6 million at

Fig. 8 Spanwise variation at an angle-of-attack of 6° in the lift-to-drag ratio (*solid lines*) and suction side transition location (*dotted*) for the FFA-W3-211 (*upper row*) and DU91-W2-250 (*lower row*) with mild and severe erosion at Reynolds numbers of 3 (*left*) and 6 million (*right*) for both aerofoils. The respective 2D clean transitional predictions are indicated by gray horizontal lines.

0° , not present at 3 million. The performance with severe erosion diverges more quickly from the clean transitional than the mild erosion as the angle-of-attack increases. Reynolds number effects are clearly seen for both aerofoils with mild erosion. At 4° the drag jumps up, away from the clean transitional, as the Reynolds number is doubled. Whereas the drag with mild erosion is bounded by the transitional and tripped, the drag with severe erosion exceeds the tripped beyond 6° , again indicating premature separation. The previously described behaviour is also clearly reflected in the glide ratio. With mild erosion it follows the transitional at a Reynolds number of 3 million until 4° —consistent between aerofoils—whereas at 6 million it already diverges and moves closely to the tripped performance. However, at the maximum glide ratio angle-of-attack, the drop is considerably at both Reynolds numbers. For severe erosion the performance mostly resembles that of the tripped, except around 0° , where it nearly reaches transitional performance. The strong increase in drag beyond 6° , causes the glide ratio to drop below that of the tripped.

2. Spanwise Transition Behaviour

The pronounced Reynolds number effects and the intermediate performance—between the clean tripped and transitional cases—observed with mild erosion suggest that the roughness is not tripping the boundary layer along the entire span. Indeed the mild erosion presents several areas with nearly no damage (see figure 5), whereas, given the spanwise homogeneity of the severe erosion, only minimal spanwise variation is anticipated. As the response to roughness is particularly critical around the design angle-of-attack (maximum glide ratio), figure 8 depicts the spanwise variation in the lift-to-drag ratio (solid lines) and superimposes the suction side transition location (dots) for both aerofoils (top, bottom) and Reynolds numbers (left, right) for the two erosion cases at an angle-of-attack of 6° . Only the suction side transition location is shown as, firstly, it most strongly affects lift and drag—it affects friction, but also the strength of the suction peak—and, secondly, because the stagnation point at this angle-of-attack moves below the erosion. Due to the smaller chordwise extent of the mild erosion, it falls below at an angle-of-attack of 2° , whilst for the severe erosion this happens at 6° [†]—this occurs independent of Reynolds number. As reference the 2D clean lift-to-drag ratio and transition locations are given as horizontal gray lines.

Focusing on mild erosion and the lower Reynolds number (left), peaks in the lift-to-drag ratio clearly correlate with the transition location—larger features are seen for both aerofoils. In the near-clean regions of the erosion patch the transition location closely approaches that of 2D clean. However, at 6 million most of the erosion has become critical, triggering transition over most of span for $x/c < 0.1$. Clearly, the severe erosion is already critical at 3 million. That mild and severe erosion approach the clean behaviour around 0° can also be attributed to the transition location approaching the 2D clean over most of the span (not shown). As modern wind turbine blades usually operate at Reynolds number above 6 million, even shallow and sparse erosion damage like the mild erosion tested herein can hence be expected to trigger transition over the entire span.

3. Drag components

Fig. 9 Contributions to pressure (*left*) and viscous drag (*right*) for the FFA-W3-211 (*upper row*) and DU91-W2-250 (*lower row*) with mild (*blue*) and severe (*red*) erosion at two Reynolds numbers; expressed as ratio of total 2D clean drag. Lines are 2D clean with free transition, tripped suction side only and fully tripped.

[†]At -4.5° the stagnation point lies above the erosion for both cases.

Away from stall, the performance loss of aerofoils with erosion predominantly stems from drag growth. When roughness triggers boundary layer transition the viscous drag increases, and, if sufficiently large, it also adds to pressure drag. Figure 9 shows the variation of the the pressure (left panel) and viscous (right panel) drag components with angle-of-attack for mild (blue) and severe (red) erosion, for both aerofoils and Reynolds numbers. The components are expressed as ratio of the total drag of the 2D clean case with free transition. As reference the corresponding clean 2D tripped and free transition components are drawn, as well as those were only the suction side is tripped. The latter indicates whether the erosion behaves like a suction side transition trigger. The 2D behaviour follows expectations, with viscous drag dominating at lower angles-of-attack. Only beyond 9° does pressure drag take-over. There is only a limited Reynolds number effect visible, that is due to transition moving forward at lower angles-of-attack, increasing the relative contributions of viscous drag. When only the suction side is tripped the drag lies between the free transition and fully tripped, moving closer to the latter. The changes due to erosion and the effect of Reynolds number is also reflected in the drag. Mild erosion does indeed behave like free transition at low lift and especially at the higher Reynolds number coincides with the partially tripped 2D results at 6° . At higher angles-of-attack the viscous drag keeps following, as the triggering is already happening right at the leading edge, however pressure drag keeps rising. The severe erosion clearly triggering transition at nearly all angles-of-attack over the suction side, except at 3 million. It does not reach the fully tripped, as the pressure side transitions freely. A stark change is seen in the pressure drag, though. Already at 4° does it reach the level of the 2D tripped and diverges from it at larger angles-of-attack, showing that severe erosion not only acts as transition trigger, but also increases pressure drag substantially.

C. 2D-3D Equivalence

Fig. 10 Lift-to-drag ratio variation with angle-of-attack for 3D simulations with the mild and severe erosion patch and 2D simulations of 11 chordwise slices extracted from the 3D surface mesh. Shaded area bounded by data range, lines denote the mean. Data shown for the FFA-W3-211 (*upper row*) and DU91-W2-250 (*lower row*) for Reynolds numbers of 3 (*left*) and 6 million (*right*); all simulations transitional, unless indicated.

Figure 10 compares the lift-over-drag polars for the 3D aerofoil sections with mild and severe leading edge erosion against the 2D simulations of chordwise slices of those same sections. The polars are generated for transitional flow in

Fig. 11 Comparison of the spanwise variation in the lift-to-drag ratio between 2D slices (dots) and 3D simulations at an angle-of-attack of 6° for the FFA-W3-211 and Reynolds numbers of 3 (left) and 6 million (right). The respective 2D clean transitional and tripped predictions are indicated by gray horizontal lines, coloured lines indicate the span-averaged value; all simulations are transitional, unless indicated.

3D and for transitional and fully turbulent (tripped) flows for the 2D slices. The polars for 2D transitional and turbulent simulations for the clean aerofoil geometries are also shown. The lines represent the mean lift-over-drag ratio of the slices over the spanwise section with the mild and severe erosions. Whereas, the shaded region shown in a lighter shade of the mean line colour represents the range of lift-over-drag values encountered for the spanwise slices of the corresponding roughness patch. Figure 11 compares the spanwise variation of the lift-to-drag ratio for the 3D aerofoil section against 2D simulations of chordwise slices for the FFA-W3-211 aerofoil with mild and severe erosion, at an angle-of-attack of 6° . The corresponding results from the fully turbulent (tripped) 2D simulations are also shown. Results are only shown for the FFA, as it is representative for both profiles.

In figure 10, for both aerofoils, the 2D transitional predictions for mild erosion (shown in green) align with the 3D up to angles-of-attack of 4° for Reynolds numbers of 3 million and till 2° for 6 million, respectively. Beyond these angles-of-attack, the 2D slices start to cover a wide range. In the mildly eroded case, some of the slices are akin to clean geometry. Consequently, the green-shaded region in figure 10 varies from lift-over-drag values that follow the clean transitional predictions to those that are close to the clean tripped predictions. This is clearly different to the 3D predictions with the mild erosion, which shows limited overlap with the 2D predictions. Unlike in 2D, the 3D CFD slices are not isolated from each other, and there is a strong “3D” effect in the onset of transition as also seen in figure 11, where some 2D results clearly behave as if clean, whereas the 3D does not. Only if the uneroded region is large enough does also the 3D start to approach clean behaviour. Thus, the 3D predictions are seen to separate earlier from the clean 2D CFD transitional predictions and also have a smaller range of values than their 2D mildly eroded counterparts.

As a consequence of the 3D effects of transition, the milder the erosion, the larger the spanwise variation in the severity of the erosion, the greater the deviation of the span-averaged 3D CFD predictions from the 2D. This observation is strengthened by the behaviour of the 2D and 3D CFD transitional predictions for the severely eroded case. As mentioned earlier the severe erosion is spanwise homogenous, thus the mean 2D and 3D CFD transitional lift-over-drag polars for both aerofoils show excellent agreement. Furthermore, the spanwise variations are lower, as demonstrated by the narrower red and yellow shaded regions corresponding to the data ranges for the 3D and 2D CFD transitional predictions for the severely eroded case, respectively. This is confirmed in figure 11, where the spanwise lift-over-drag predictions are seen to coincide with severe erosion for both Reynolds numbers. As the mild erosion case strongly depends on capturing the transition triggering effect of roughness, the fully turbulent simulations of the 2D slices do not match the 3D at all. However, as severe erosion acts as an effective transition trigger, they do seem to capture the span-averaged behaviour beyond an angle-of-attack of 6° , yet at least with the slices selected here, the range cannot be matched.

Figure 12 shows the four roughness profiles that were applied to the aerofoils between $-0.04 \leq y/c \leq -0.01$ and

run in 2D CFD. Of special interest here is that two of the profiles from the mild erosion only trigger transition once at a Reynolds number of 6 million, so they turned *critical* as the boundary layer thinned down. The other two either did not trigger or always triggered transition. For the severe case, the depth of the damages are at least four times as large as the worst from the mild patch (plotted in gray as reference) and thus are always critical. Using the clean transitional 2D simulations, the boundary layer thickness at a Reynolds number of 3 million for $2 \text{ mm} \leq s \leq 6 \text{ mm}$ is about 0.3 mm, meaning that the damage is about the same size. At 6 million the boundary layer thins down to about 0.2 mm, meaning that the damages are exceeding the boundary layer height.

Fig. 12 Roughness profiles of four selected span locations from the mild (*left*) and severe (*right*) erosion maps. The mild profiles are shown in gray on the right.

IV. Conclusion

Two roughness topographies recently extracted from high-resolution 3D scans of leading edge roughness/erosion on wind turbine blades were applied to two commonly used wind turbine aerofoils with 21% and 25% relative thickness and evaluated in steady-state 3D RANS CFD. The two topographies are very distinct, with one exhibiting a sparse distribution of damages of limited depth ($\leq 0.8 \text{ mm}$) towards the suction side and the other deep, spanwise-uniform erosion ($\leq 4 \text{ mm}$) with sharp forward facing steps and overhangs. The 3D CFD simulations showed that mild erosion mainly acts as a transition trigger, however only on the suction side over operational angles-of-attack, as the stagnation point moves below the eroded region. With increasing Reynolds number even small damages ($\approx 0.4 \text{ mm}$) become critical and the transition spreads to neighbouring near-undamaged regions of the leading edge. Decomposing the drag into pressure and viscous contributions, confirmed that mild erosion essentially acts as transition trigger. Severe erosion on the other hand not only triggers transition, but also leads to a stark increase in pressure drag, far beyond that just seen from triggering. Whilst the span extent herein is not large enough to accurately capture stall, it strongly resembles the pre-stall behaviour observed for severe forms of icing [32].

To test whether 2D simulations could be used to evaluate the aerodynamic effects of erosion, additionally a limited number of 2D chordwise slices were extracted from the eroded 3D aerofoil and simulated. As a consequence of the previously mentioned three-dimensionality of transition, the milder the erosion, the larger the spanwise variation in the severity of the erosion, and hence the greater the deviation between 2D and 3D predictions.

For more general recommendations on how to evaluate the aerodynamic effects of erosion, boundary layer quantities will be extracted and correlated with roughness parameters in the future.

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References

- [1] Sareen, A., Sapre, C. A., and Selig, M. S., “Effects of leading edge erosion on wind turbine blade performance,” *Wind Energy*, Vol. 17, No. 10, 2014, pp. 1531–1542. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/we.1649>, URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/we.1649>.
- [2] Gaudern, N., “A practical study of the aerodynamic impact of wind turbine blade leading edge erosion,” *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, Vol. 524, No. 1, 2014, p. 012031. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/524/1/012031>, URL <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/524/1/012031>.
- [3] Langel, C. M., Chow, R. C., van Dam, C. P., and Maniaci, D. C., “RANS Based Methodology for Predicting the Influence of Leading Edge Erosion on Airfoil Performance,” 2017. <https://doi.org/10.2172/1404827>, URL <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1404827>.
- [4] Meyer Forsting, A., Olsen, A. S., Sørensen, N. N., and Bak, C., “The impact of leading edge damage and repair on sectional aerodynamic performance,” *AIAA SCITECH Forum*, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2023-0968>.
- [5] Ehrmann, R. S., Wilcox, B., White, E. B., and Maniaci, D. C., “Effect of Surface Roughness on Wind Turbine Performance,” Tech. rep., Sandia National Lab.(SNL-NM), Albuquerque, NM (United States), 2017.
- [6] Ortolani, A., Castorrini, A., and Campobasso, M. S., “Multi-scale Navier-Stokes analysis of geometrically resolved erosion of wind turbine blade leading edges,” *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, Vol. 2265, IOP Publishing, 2022, p. 032102.
- [7] Vimalakanthan, K., van der Mijle Meijer, H., Bakhmet, I., and Schepers, G., “Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) modeling of actual eroded wind turbine blades,” *Wind Energy Science*, Vol. 8, No. 1, 2023, pp. 41–69.
- [8] Schrauf, G., “On allowable surface tolerances for laminar flow,” , June 2022.
- [9] Forsting, A. M., Olsen, A., Sørensen, N., Fischer, A., Markussen, C., and Bak, C., “An aerodynamic digital twin of real-world leading edge erosion: Acquisition, Generation and 3D CFD,” *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, Vol. 2767, No. 2, 2024, p. 022021. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2767/2/022021>, URL <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2767/2/022021>.
- [10] Stebbins, S., Loth, E., Broeren, A., Potapczuk, M., and Porter, C., “Aerodynamics of a common research model wing with leading-edge ice shape,” *Journal of Aircraft*, Vol. 58, No. 4, 2021, pp. 894–906.
- [11] Stebbins, S., and Loth, E., *Numerical Simulation of Iced Swept Wing Aerodynamics with RANS, DES, and IDDES*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2023, pp. 1–22. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-64725-4_6-1, URL https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-64725-4_6-1.
- [12] Bons, J. P., McClain, S. T., Wang, Z. J., Chi, X., and Shih, T. I., “A Comparison of Approximate Versus Exact Geometrical Representations of Roughness for CFD Calculations of cf and St,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 130, No. 2, 2008, p. 021024. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2752190>, URL <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2752190>.
- [13] Meyer Forsting, A., Troldborg, N., and Gaunaa, M., “The flow upstream of a row of aligned wind turbine rotors and its effect on power production,” *Wind Energy*, Vol. 20, No. 1, 2017, p. 63–77. <https://doi.org/10.1002/we.1991>.
- [14] Keunseok Lee, J. B., Heejeon Im, and Kim, B., “Analysis of variations in annual energy production based on types of suction side erosion at the blade tip of a wind turbine using numerical simulation,” *International Journal of Green Energy*, Vol. 21, No. 1, 2023, pp. 74–86.
- [15] Björck, A., *Coordinates and Calculations for the FFA-W1-xxx, FFA-W2-xxx and FFA-W3-xxx Series of Airfoils for Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines*, Aeronautical Research Institute of Sweden, 1990.
- [16] *Summary of the Delft University Wind Turbine Dedicated Airfoils*, Wind Energy Symposium, Vol. ASME 2003 Wind Energy Symposium, 2003. <https://doi.org/10.1115/WIND2003-352>, URL <https://doi.org/10.1115/WIND2003-352>.
- [17] Zahle, F., “Parametric Geometric Library for Wind (PGLW),” , 2022. URL <https://gitlab.windenergy.dtu.dk/frza/PGL>.
- [18] Sørensen, N., “HypGrid2D a 2-D Mesh Generator,” Tech. Rep. Risø-R-1035(EN), RisøNational Laboratory, 1998.
- [19] Michelsen, J. A., “Basis3D—a platform for development of multiblock PDE solvers,” Tech. Rep. AFM 92-05, Technical University of Denmark, 1992.
- [20] Sørensen, N., “General purpose flow solver applied to flow over hills,” Tech. Rep. Risø-R-827(EN), RisøNational Laboratory, 1995.

- [21] Kolmogorov, D. K., Shen, W. Z., Sørensen, N. N., and Sørensen, J. N., “Fully consistent SIMPLE-like algorithms on collocated grids,” *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part B: Fundamentals*, Vol. 67, No. 2, 2015, pp. 101–123.
- [22] Leonard, B., “A stable and accurate convective modelling procedure based on quadratic upstream interpolation,” *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, Vol. 19, 1979, pp. 59–98.
- [23] Menter, F. R., Kuntz, M., Langtry, R., et al., “Ten years of industrial experience with the SST turbulence model,” *Turbulence, heat and mass transfer*, Vol. 4, No. 1, 2003, pp. 625–632.
- [24] van Ingen, J., “Suggested Semi-Empirical Method for the Calculation of the Boundary Layer Transition Region,” Tech. Rep. Delft Univ. of Technology Rept. VTH-74, Dept. of Aerospace Engineering, 1956.
- [25] Smith, A., and Gamberoni, N., “Transition, Pressure Gradient, and Stability Theory,” Tech. Rep. Douglas Aircraft Rept. ES-26388, 1956.
- [26] Drela, M., and Giles, M. B., “Viscous-inviscid analysis of transonic and low Reynolds number airfoils,” *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 25, No. 10, 1987, pp. 1347–1355. <https://doi.org/10.2514/3.9789>, URL <https://doi.org/10.2514/3.9789>.
- [27] Michelsen, Jess A., *Forskning i aeroelasticitet (Research in aeroelasticity) EFP-2001*, Risø-R-1349(DA), Forskningscenter Risø (now DTU Wind), 2002, Chaps. 6. Beregning af laminar-turbulent omslag i 2D og 3D (Computation of laminar-turbulent transition in 2D and 3D).
- [28] Langtry, R. B., and Menter, F. R., “Correlation-based transition modeling for unstructured parallelized computational fluid dynamics codes,” *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 47, No. 12, 2009, pp. 2894–2906.
- [29] Kato, M., and Launder, B., “The modelling of turbulent flow around stationary and vibrating square cylinders,” paper 10-4, August 1993. 9th Symposium on Turbulent Shear Flows, Kyoto, Japan.
- [30] Spalart, P. R., and Rumsey, C. L., “Effective Inflow Conditions for Turbulence Models in Aerodynamic Calculations,” *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 45, No. 10, 2007, pp. 2544–2553.
- [31] Mack, L. M., “Transition and laminar instability,” Tech. Rep. JPL-PUBL-77-15, 1977.
- [32] Bornhoft, B., Jain, S. S., Goc, K., Bose, S. T., and Moin, P., “Large-eddy simulations of the NACA23012 airfoil with laser-scanned ice shapes,” *Aerospace Science and Technology*, Vol. 146, 2024, p. 108957. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2024.108957>, URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1270963824000907>.
- [33] DTU Computing Center, “DTU Computing Center resources,” , 2021. <https://doi.org/10.48714/DTU.HPC.0001>, URL <https://doi.org/10.48714/DTU.HPC.0001>.